

FRANTZ FANON AND THE POSTCOLONIAL AESTHETICS

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Abstract

Critics have emphasised Frantz Fanon's contributions to the emergence of what is today known as the postcolonial literature. His writings have laid the foundation of its theory and practice. One of the areas that is still generating debates is the area of aesthetics of postcolonial literature. Some critics have suggested that the only way to have a fruitful exploration of the aesthetic aspect of postcolonial literature is to combine Kant's theory of aesthetics with Fanon's. Fanon emphasises the development of postcolonial writers from his immersion into colonial culture to his rebellion against same leading to his incomplete intellectual emancipation thus establishing the field as a centre of political and cultural commitment. This does not mean that the field does not possess its own aesthetics or that Fanon was silent on it. Boehmer and Ashcroft have identified language of the postcolonial text as its aesthetics. This paper traces the development of the postcolonial theory and its aesthetics from its beginning through the thoughts expanded by Frantz Fanon to unearth some other postcolonial aesthetic parameters. The paper employs postcolonial theory as its theoretical framework. The findings of this paper are though politics is at the center of the postcolonial literature, this does not negate its aesthetic commitment right from its foundation in the works of Frantz Fanon. Postcolonial aesthetics is not just restricted to the language of the postcolonial texts. There are other parameters like song, history and performance constitute the postcolonial aesthetics as exemplified in the works of Kamau Brathwaite.

Key word: Postcolonial, Aesthetics, Frantz Fanon, History, Language

Introduction

Postcolonial writers, in both theories and creative writings, have viewed the idea of aesthetics with nostalgia because of the claim of its universality by western philosophers and that aesthetics theory might, in some ways, compromise the political consciousness/agenda of the field. As Ashcroft (2015) succinctly puts it:

Postcolonial theory has warily avoided the theory of aesthetics, perhaps for fear that it might contaminate the political integrity of a field that has remained staunchly critical of the filiative hegemony of English literature. Obviously, postcolonial art and literature can, like

any other creative production, be considered in aesthetic terms. But whether a “postcolonial aesthetic” exists as a discrete category is highly unlikely, as unlikely as a specific postcolonial ontology or postcolonial style (P. 410).

Ashcroft’s (2015) position points to ongoing controversies in the field of postcolonial literature and aesthetics. However, there is that silent acceptance, among postcolonial critics that postcolonial writings, like other cultural and artistic materials, possess their own aesthetics that vary from the notion of the aesthetics conceived by western arts philosophers and critics (Nasir, 2019). Following Boehmer’s (2010) advice, there is need to explore what constitutes the aesthetics of postcolonial writings, may be, more knowledge would be unearthed in the process.

Defining the term ‘postcolonial aesthetics’ and what constitutes the aesthetics have remained a challenge to the theorists and practitioners in the field. Some critics like Boehmer (2010) have avoided giving a prescriptive definition of the term probably because of its political implication of postcolonialism. After citing and critiquing some major postcolonial theorists, she gives what can be described as explanation of the term:

Perhaps there is that within a postcolonial aesthetic that clarifies or sheds light on the postcolonial condition, be it hybrid or manichean, though without necessarily setting out to do so, without overt intention, without set and specific interest. There is that within an aesthetic that we might call postcolonial that draws in the postcolonial world, imbibes its affect, and constellates and reconstellates its meanings through our reading of it, our participation in it ... there is that within an aesthetic which we might want to call postcolonial, that catalyses a post-humanist or non-western humanism, though again this effect is largely incidental – the process plays itself out with mostly unanticipated consequences (p. 174).

She later emphasises the centrality of language in any discussion of postcolonial aesthetics by stating that “The postcolonial aesthetic,” she writes, “then, is *in* language rather than *of* language, it requires participation from readers, it draws us into a process that makes possible certain kinds of postcolonial understanding (p. 180).”

Ashcroft views provide a more elaborate definition of postcolonial aesthetics. However, like Boehmer, he also emphasised the centrality of the hybrid language of the postcolonial texts. According to him, the aesthetic “lies in the materiality of the language, for this is the space of contact between cultures” (p.415). He defines the postcolonial aesthetic as “transformative affective space” constituted by the hybridity of the language of the postcolonial literary text (p. 416).

Apart from being one of the first philosophers to explore the conditions of the Blacks in the White dominated world, Fanon as a psychiatrist used his professional experience to look into the damaging effect of colonialism and imperialism on Blacks. He was also concerned about how these factors have contributed to the exploitation and oppression of them with their effects on formation of identity. He was unpretentious in prescribing the right antidote against the white oppression and exploitation in his book *The Wretched of the Earth* (1965) in which he advocates violence to dismantle the whites’ organized dominance and oppression. His philosophy is emancipative, liberative and restorative. He insisted that “violence alone, violence committed by

the people, violence organized and educated by its leaders, makes it possible for the masses to understand social truths and gives the key to them” (p. 188). Postcolonial creative writers are then admonished, through Fanon’s thesis to embrace aesthetics that would instigate the masses to act against the masters’ oppression and exploitation.

This paper is an attempt to examine Frantz Fanon’s contributions to what is today conceived as the postcolonial aesthetics with focus on Kamau Brathwaite’s two major poetry collections, *The Arrivants* (1967) and *Born to Slow Horses* (2005). *The Arrivants* was written early in his career and the former was written at the closing phase. The choice of the two texts is to allow us trace the poet’s development as Caribbean’s native writer and his aesthetic choices at different stages of his writings conforms to Fanon’s model.

Origin of the Postcolonial Aesthetics

Though Fanon’s *Black skin, white masks* (1952) and *The Wretched of the Earth* (1963) were written as a critique of the colonialism and its impacts in the erstwhile colonial settlements, some cultural critics have traced the origin of the “postcolonial aesthetics” to these two texts. In the first text, Fanon envisions three stages of native literary and cultural development. The cycle begins with the native’s exposure to colonialism through to his moment of total freedom. He calls the first stage the “period of unqualified assimilation” which works show complete assimilation of coloniser’s culture and writing system. Such literary productions imitate in totality the standard of the colonisers showing that the native writers completely embraces the culture of the center. The native intellectual “has thrown himself greedily upon western culture” (Fanon, 1967, P.176). He added that the native writers at this stage in their work “correspond point by point with those of their respective numbers in their mother country” (pp. 178-179). He concludes that the literatures produced at this stage are not only influenced by the colonial masters’ culture, they also mimic every aspect of their literature: “For not only are Western literary forms reproduced, but even the content of such literature reflects Western colonial attitudes and cultural practices”. In one of his articles, Fanon asserts “West Indians and North Africans”, he castigates all West Indian literatures produced before Aime Cesaire as “a literature of Europeans” and concludes that “Until 1939 the West Indian lived, thought, dreamt, composed poems, wrote novels exactly as a white man would have done ...The West Indian identified himself with the white man, adopted a white man’s attitude and “was a white man.” (1969, p. 26).

The second stage is described as the dialectical antithesis of the first stage by Al-Abbood (2012). The stage precedes the emergence of a full-fledged concerted efforts towards decolonisation in the colony. The literatures are characterised by the misinterpretation of ‘post-times’ and old legends “in the light of a borrowed aestheticism and a conception of the world which was discovered under other skies”. It is the beginning of the awareness of who the native writer is and there is that pressure to do away with the knowledge in which he had been indoctrinated. He craves to return to his people despite realising he could not fully return to the fully lived experience. Fanon asserts that the native writer could not go beyond just recalling the experience as the previous indoctrination prevents him from being completely re-immersed into the people’s life and culture. What he shares with his root is just the “superficial” and “exterior”. Having realised the futility of his effort to return completely to his previous state/culture, he now chooses to become the protector and champion of his people’s revolutionary life. “Turns himself into an awakener of the people. He associates with his people’s efforts to liberate themselves from the claws of colonialism. He is

not only there to shape his people's consciousness, but he also becomes their mouthpiece of a new reality in action" (P.179)

The above stages constructed by Fanon has been widely claimed as the origin of what would be tagged later as 'the postcolonial aesthetics' by some postcolonial critics. For instance, Holdridge (2001) combines Fanon's postulation with Emmanuel Kant's to form what he calls Fanonite/Kantian stages to arrive at the postcolonial sublime. The submission by Holdridge (2001) is an effort to explain postcolonial aesthetics. In his words,

Politically, there are three Fanonite/Kantian stages to what is here termed the postcolonial sublime. It is an aesthetic that aligns Fanon's dialectic of decolonisation, from occupation, through nationalism, to liberation with Kant's three stages of sublimity, that is, from balance between subject and object, through aesthetic violence upon the internal sense, to transcendental compensation (2001, p. 189).

Holdridge's maintains that Fanon has consciously formulated an enduring theory on native writers' affiliation to his culture and colonialism aesthetically and ideologically when his position is aligned with that of Kant.

While Fanon emphasises the development of postcolonial writers from his immersion into colonial culture to his rebellion against same leading to his incomplete intellectual emancipation, Kant (1987) submits that when beauty is affirmed of the object, there is additional content to this affirmation, namely the ability of the object to provide satisfaction to those who judge it disinterestedly. Holdridge (2001) posits here that the Fanon's notion of postcolonial writer's stages of development should be combined with Kant's aesthetics judgement to unearth what constitutes postcolonial aesthetics. Weiner (1994), Boehmer, (2010) and Ashcroft (2015) also corroborate Kant's aesthetics notion but without recourse to Fanon's writings. That is, the foundation of their arguments for the existence of postcolonial aesthetics is located in the Kant's theory of aesthetics.

However, adopting Kant's (1987) aesthetics notion without considering the colonial and cultural experiences of the erstwhile colonial states would create knowledge stampede because Kant's notion of aesthetics is rooted in the Western cultural history and experience. In other words, his aesthetics theory cannot cater for the non-Western notion of aesthetics.

In order to locate the idea of the aesthetics that varies from the western's 'beauty of judgment', Gerbrands (1976) comes up with the idea of 'ethno-aesthetics' which, according to him, was first used by Dark (cited in Van Damme 1991, p. 172) as the cross-cultural study of art, a means of coming to grip with what has been termed tribal or primitive arts "in the totality of its context and history, meaning and form, and the person and character of the individual creator". As an anthropological term, ethno-aesthetics is reserved for the study of the pre-literate arts rather than the current postcolonial discourse. There is then the need to extend it to other arts occurring in space and/or time without necessarily using objects like dance music, oral literature etc (Van Damme 1991, p. 174).

According to Fanon, language remains one of the major sites of colonial subjugation and atrocities. The contact between the colonial master and the colonised has, in no small measure, aided European languages' prominence in Africa and the world at large – it has unarguably contributed to the development of the English language as a global language. While this has benefited the

colonisers, the development is seen in the erstwhile colonies as disruption in the identity formation. In his seminal work on colonialism, Fanon (1963) discusses extensively the place and importance of language to both the European masters and the colonised in the colonial regime. Fanon (1963) identifies language as the major means through which the master succeeded in separating black children from their cultural values. He unequivocally argues that European languages are tools of oppression and dehumanisation, which put the destinies of the colonised in the control of the colonial regime.

In the history of literature, there are varied examples of the colonised adopting the colonial language as a medium of communication. In fiction, Friday is taught English in Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe* (1719). In drama, Shakespeare's Caliban, the indigenous of the island, provides a well-known example of such a strategy in *The Tempest* (1623). "You taught me language, and my profit on't/ Is, I know how to curse: the real plague rid you / For learning me your language" (p. 39). Caliban tells the foreign Prospero. This strategy of creatively adopting and adapting the language of the 'other' to create "a synthetic revolutionary culture in place of the bastardised or eradicated indigenous culture of the colonised" (Soyinka 1993, p. 139) had a strong appeal to Soyinka who called for exposing the coloniser's language to a deliberate process of appropriation to answer the local needs of the natives.

While African poets returned to their own languages and culture to 'appropriate' the Standard English to suit their literary demands, the Caribbean story is different. Hardly do poets in the Caribbean have a single native language to return to. After being conveyed to the 'new world' the colonisers were prohibited the slaves from using their language. This was to suppress any possible revolt against the colonisers. The English language was imposed to replace the tribal languages of the slaves. Thus, the people had to communicate with what Glissant calls a 'forced poetics' which gives rise to inconsistency between the lived experience and its expression in an alien system of signification. For linguistic survival, the slaves, followed by their descendants had to form their own languages "as antidotes, a non-neutral one through which the problems of the community can be restated" (Dash 1989, p. x). The submerged language which has a tendency for cultural resistance is tagged 'nation language' by Brathwaite. Brathwaite's work (1984) gives details of the emergence, operations and relations to the English language in the Anglophone Caribbean.

Brathwaite (1984) defines the nation language as the language which is influenced very strongly by mode of African New World/Caribbean heritage. It may be English in terms of its lexical features. But in its contours, its rhythm and timbre, its sound explosions, it is not English, even though the words, as you hear them might be English to a greater or lesser degree... it is not English that is the agent, it is not language, but people who make evolutions (p. 13).

As an alternative to the English language, nation language becomes a tool that could be used to represent the Caribbean consciousness in no way English language could. Its subversive quality makes it more appealing to the people. While the coloniser wants the colonised to speak his language and receive its values, the colonised produces a distorted version of his linguistic registers.

Throughout his time at Cambridge, Brathwaite was writing poetry and getting it published in Caribbean journals (Rohlehr 1981, p. 4). From his first published poem ('Shadow Suite', Elm no.

12, June 1950), he shows a desire to use jazz and other musical forms as structural models, developing a theme through a number of 'variations'. He also reacted to 'the 'colonial' breakthrough...achieved by Eliot, Pound and Joyce (Brathwaite 1967, p. 39). He saw himself at this stage as the "universal man"; to be West Indian "meant you were being parochial." (cited in Perrier 1973, p. 37). His fixation with these Euro-modernist poems and their works suggests his love for their language use. At the early stage of his career as a poet, he was accused of following their styles. But his themes are rooted in the Caribbean history and environment. He was fascinated by jazz and the roars of the sea. Most of his poetic materials are bound within the Islands. He said, "I read Keats, Conrad, Kafka. I was a man of Kulture. But the Cambridge magazines didn't take my poems, rather, they only took those which had a West Indian — to me, 'exotic' — flavour. I felt rejected and misunderstood". (Brathwaite, 1970, P. 37).

After his education in Pembroke, he felt there was no need to return home. He could stay in England, nurture his talents as a writer and succeed like Samuel Selvon, George Lamming and Wilson Harris. However, his efforts at finding job did not yield any result: "Accepting my rootlessness, I applied for work in London, Cambridge, Ceylon, New Delhi, Cairo, Kano, Khartoum, Sierra Leone, Caracassone, a monastery in Jerusalem. I was a West Indian, roofless man of the world". (Brathwaite, 1970, p. 38). He got a job in Ghana in 1955 as Education Officer, a role and adventure that watered his vision and literary inspiration about the continent and culture he had embraced. His works have reflected a new direction after his sojourn in Ghana. According to him, his Ghana experience laid to rest his search for identity and marks the end of his rootlessness. Henceforth, Africa and her past became the sources for his literary inspiration and artistic vision.

Brathwaite's Poetry and the Postcolonial Aesthetics: *The Arrivants* and *Born to Slow Horses*

Many critics recognise Brathwaite's rich use of the African oral poetics, history and African cultural devices in *The Arrivants*. Bodunde (1994 and 2001), Griffith (2010) and Savory (2011) emphasise orality as the main frame on which the collection is built and sustained. Bodunde (1994) identifies the oral aesthetics as "a significant aspect of Braithwaite's portrayal of African essence and imaginative transfer of African aesthetic materials in order to realise poems which are truly African in content and form. Prominent among these aesthetics and cultural products are praise tradition, ritual chants, and dirges" (p. 28).

The Arrivants draws upon a wide range of traditional African oral poetic and cultural elements. Along with Creole, Brathwaite incorporates other oral musical elements such as calypso, drum poetry, flute poetry, and libation poetry all of which foreground the religious significance of the poetry. It should be observed that these features are not new in the Caribbean poetry. All these elements are consistently used to confirm the links between Africa and the diaspora and they point to the poet's effort to forge a new identity for the blacks in the diaspora. The compositions of all these poems are influenced constantly by oral/aural demands.

Rohler (1981, p. 78) illustrates the way Brathwaite uses refrain as, two pages on, the same words and form are echoed and elaborated:

So I who have created
nothing but these worthless
weeds, these need-
less seeds, work;

who have built
but on silt, but on sand,
but on luckless salt
dream;
who have forgotten all
mouth 'Massa, yes
Massa, yes
Boss, yes
Baas' (*The Arrivants*, p. 15)

Rohler's examples of the simple worksong form and its elaborated 'refrain' illustrate Brathwaite's equivalent of a jazz, the repetition of a 'theme' (Brathwaite 1967/8, p. 147). Repetition of 'theme' must involve repetition of all or some words because in Brathwaite's terms, words become the equivalent of notes. Thinking of words as notes also opened Brathwaite's mind to the suggestiveness of words as sound, bringing new possibilities of meaning through association. He uses his own 'Calypso' (1973 p. 48) as an example:

curved stone hissed into reef
white teeth fanged into clay
Bathsheba Montego Bay

Rhythm in *The Arrivants* is aptly dispatched to communicate blacks' historical and cultural experiences and identity as witnessed by the poet. The rhythm of the Caribbean song, especially reggae and the calypso, is also conceptualised in 'Ancestors':

Come - a look
come - a look
see wha' happen
sookey dead
sookey dead
sookey dead o
sookey dead
sookey dead
sookey dead o
him a - wuk
him a - wuk
till 'e bleed o. (*The Arrivants*, p. 240)

Brathwaite identifies jazz essentially as sounds of freedom; "the Emancipated Negro's music" (1967, p. 275). He contrasts this with the worksong and blues, as characterising the conditions of slavery. A key element of the jazz performance is improvisation; a quality shared with much oral poetry of Africa (see, for example Nketia 1955), with African-Creole story-telling and other oral traditions (Brathwaite 1967/8, p. 2) and, in fact, with many aspects of folk performance throughout the world. While much folk improvisation is heavily formulaic, however, jazz is much less predictable; "the jazz listener is perpetually faced with an unknown future" (Brathwaite 1967, p. 143). It is in this respect that jazz is more essentially bound up with the notion of freedom. Association primarily by sound is a characteristic of the oral mode. Brathwaite has developed a method of improvisation on the individual word through sound association which offers new

possibilities for thought and ideas. In breaking down more traditional sequences of thought he is composing in a way which has much in common with jazz. “Jah” is carefully patterned on the idea of a jazz band in performance.

"Wings of a Dove', 'Caliban' and 'Ancestors' are all instances of song and dance. The poet uses songs deliberately as a feature of style to give rhythm and express the Calibans' folk style. There is the use of jazz and blues, putting language in songs to communicate various realities of the Caribbean Island culture. This is common in oral narratives to enliven the narration and engage the audience by activating them to join in the singing, nod or even dance to the rhythm of the song; thus, livening up the performance. At times these songs are used in the trilogy to instigate the arrivants into action by deliberately citing brutal, painful and personal disasters experienced in arrivants' daily life.

Born to Slow Horses (2005) is one of Brathwaite's later works. Like *The Arrivants*, the collection centres on Caribbean situation. However, its thematic preoccupation extends to the world affairs. Brathwaite uses *Born to Slow Horses* (2005) to mourn the victims of September 2001 terrorists attack in the United States of America. Subsumed in this is also the death of his son, a personal tragedy and the voice of a slave woman buried in Barbados long ago without proper ritual rites. We can say death remains a common concept in this poem like in his other poems. “Brathwaite's poetry has always been aware of the dead ... his work locates the dead with the living, especially the dead whose lives were damaged or suddenly ended by violence” (Savory 2011, p. 15).

Language, above other aesthetic parameters is presented in *Born to Slow Horses* as site of tension in Caribbean literature. It is a site where Brathwaite makes his linguistic choice clear as he rejects the common English language practices and replace them with his own form of linguistic experimentations he evolved through the nation language. Brathwaite affirms that his concern is basically with the word, both written and spoken. In other words, they are concerned with the struggle to represent their people's literary and historical experiences in writing without losing its orality, which is the primary basis of their literatures. In pursuit of this vision, Brathwaite invented the “Sycorax Video Style”, which according to him, can be used to describe Caribbean experiences of slavery, indenture and fragmentation. He thus designed a Caribbean linguistic answer to the English language question with the aid of his nation language.

Sycorax Video Style is an aspect of Brathwaite's rebellion against the dominant role of English language in the Caribbean culture and education. It involves intentional deviations from English standard grammatical rules and other nonconventional practices to subvert it. For instance, in most of Brathwaite's poems, there are prevalent uses of different fonts in the same poem, typographical breaks, icons, images all of which are made possible by the use of his nation language or Creole. The importance of the style is emphasised by Griffiths (2013) when she says that “What his (Brathwaite's) Sycorax Video Style does is to cement for us how distinctive our speech is from English, it is symbolic of a struggle of displacement, fragmentation and exploitation, and of strength of the Caribbean people in constructing ways to survive and triumph collectively” (p. 2).

To achieve poetry that counters European tradition of writing, postcolonial poets deploy visual aspects of poetry to accompany its voice system in support of the thematic concerns of the poets. Brathwaite calls the word processing tools that enable the writing of orality “nuances of language”.

They include fonts, line (dis)placements, typeface, typographic symbols, wordplay and page margins and these become means of distortion to build up Afro-Caribbean “kingdoms of the word” (Nair 2005). With his experimentation with words, Brathwaite tries to form a new linguistic order. “He uses the printed page as if it were sound where written poetry is a raid on border between the inner and outer voices, what is heard and what remains in the mind” (James 1994, p. 73). The speaking “I” or the collective “we” in the poems of these postcolonial poets implies the “location and locution of poetic voice” that “repeat[s] and reverberate[s] across historically specific moments of the minority predicament” (Bhabha 2006, p. xxii). The speaking subject tries to appropriate an interstitial place in the “uncanny fluency of another’s language” (ibid. p. 199). All these styles are impossible without the adoption of the nation language (Natasha 2008). For instance, there is intentional and radical departure from the Standard English structural rules.

The deviations and radical adoption of unconventional use of English language is noticeable right from the content page of *Born to Slow Horses*. A critical reading of the names of titles and their arrangements quickly offers the audience what to expect in the work. Brathwaite’s linguistic and typography system offers a critique of dominant approaches to history and how history is inscribed. Readers begin to encounter Brathwaite’s intentional deviations in the arrangement of the content page. The collection is in seven major divisions with the omission of section seven which is replaced with 9/11, all with varying fonts. The titles are informed from English language, history, and Brathwaite’s own creativity. Bermudas is a British colony named after the explorer, Juan de Bermudas. Guanahani was the first Island sighted and visited by Christopher Columbus on October 12, 1492. Donna is an Italian name for woman. Mmassaccourraaman is a name of Guyanese legend of the monstrous river snake. Kumina is a religion which is associated with the Africans in the Caribbean. Namsetoura is the most significant of all the non-English titles because the name comes from Brathwaite’s conception of Caribbean identity through naming.

“Naming” the new world with the appropriation of signs is a common practice among Caribbean poets. Walcott (1996) asserts that the language of poetry opposes colonial ideology and its established institutions. Thus, people that were subdued under slavery and indenture are to rename the nouns. “the process of renaming, or finding new metaphors, is the same process that the poet faces every morning of his working day, making his own tools like Crusoe, assembling nouns from necessity...even renaming himself” (p. 506-7). Bhabha (2006) defines this strategy as “the right to signify” that provides a medium of agency:

[A] specifically postcolonial performance of re-inscription, the focus shifts from nominalism of imperialism to the emergence of other sign of agency and identity. It signifies the destiny of culture as a site, not simply of subversion and transgression, but one that prefigures a kind of solidarity between ethnicities that meet in the tryst of colonial history (p. 331).

Brathwaite proffers an alternative name for “Nyam”. It becomes central to Brathwaite’s understanding of the agency of naming in *X/Self*. He explains in his notes to *X/Self* that “nam” or “nyam” is “*indestructible self/sense of culture under crisis*” (p. 127, emphasis original). Brathwaite searches for the root of this word throughout *X/Self*. “Nam” is ‘man’ in disguise when written backwards “man/nam” or “the *main* or *mane* of *name* after the weak ‘e’ or tail has been eaten by the conquistador.” Apart from these connotations, it might denote the future potential of “atomic explosion: nam...dynamo...dynamite and apotheosis: nam...nyam...onyame...” (*X/Self*, p. 127).

The meaning of “Nam” is appropriated by moving from one image to another. The first lines of “Nam” represent the African man with cinematic images:

hot cinema tarzan sweat
rolling moth ball eyes yellow teeth
cries of claws slashes clanks (*X/self*, p. 73).

African people are ironically described as savage and demonic.

Namsetoura is derived from “name” and “stories” – the story of name - Brathwaite gives the name the ghost that appeared to him at Cow Pastor. However, ‘Nam’ means more to Brathwaite’s poetry. Brathwaite’s name for “originary” or virtual world which is neither a “there” nor “property” is *nam*, an “in-dwelling man-inhabiting organic force” of any concrete cultural milieu”. It is a genetic force that has no part, cannot be divided, partitioned or parcel without changing its nature. He compares *nam* with

grit and pebbles seed safe secret
-Unquestioned not necessarily visible-
of which strength comes, where the heart
of the culture resides in its orderness (*Golokwati* 2002, p. 238)

In an interview in 2005, Brathwaite explains *nam* as a “concept of the mind which is opposite of man’s mind. ‘Man’ spelt backward, as ‘nam’ also means an imperishable spirit; so ‘man’ is a distortion of ‘nam’. And Namse is a version of Anansi the Spider. So the Spider is part of ‘Nam’ and the ‘Nam’ is part of the Spider. And ‘toura’ is a way of telling stories.” (p. 3). Thus, Brathwaite subverts the original English word ‘name’ to create *nam* in his search for the Caribbean original identity. *Nam* has been a central subject in *Ancestors*. His concern is not just on the linguistic meaning of the *nam*. It is clear that part of the value of *nam* is its graphic form – its utopic reach.

Brathwaite develops many strategies on word level to play upon the meaning of words and discover other possible meanings. Firstly, the meanings of words are used against themselves through puns, neologisms and made-up phrases. As Chamberlin (1995) argues, these strategies “reflect a deep seriousness about the ways in which words determine our representations of self and our perception of others” (p. 33). Like *X/self*, *Born to Slow Horses* is full of puns, neologisms and catachrestic use of the Prospero’s language.

Ashcroft, Tiffen and Griffiths (2001) argue that development of neologisms in postcolonial text is one of the tactics of syntactic fusion that becomes “a sign of the co-existivity between language and cultural space, and are important features of the development of English variants” (p. 71). Neologism is the use of made-up words or new words. Brathwaite deploys many words that are strange to the English standard lexicon. In ‘Guanahani’ “odales” much like “xpectation” and “landscap” is a neologism (made-up/new words) or portmanteaux that combines “oh” and “dales” (meaning valley) but ellipses the “h” for musical effect. Symbolically, “x” is scattered all around the poems taking the place of the prefix “ex-”. For instance, inxtricably (p. 9), xpose (p. 11), xplode and xplore (p. 17), unxpecting (p. 23), xhausted (p. 48), xile (p. 48), nxt (49), unXpecting (p. 73) are common words in this collection. Other words derived from intentional twisting or disorganizing the correct spellings include swimmming (p. 2), bubbelling (p. 3), freize (p. 8), askanancy (p. 9), freeling (p. 11), cosmograms (p. 12), cirrus (p. 14), uttarest (p. 48), miggle

(occurs in many instances) to replace or complement middle, fubgeting (p. 36) and scarifice (p. 60). At times, the use of these forms nearly creates ambiguity in readers' minds provoking creative thoughts in order to arrive at Brathwaite's intended meaning.

Brathwaite also uses abbreviations that are not recognised in the Standard English writing. Most auxiliary verbs are reduced to two alphabets. "Would" is written as "wd"; "could" becomes "cd"; "should" becomes "sd" and the relative pronoun "which" becomes "wc". When the preposition "with" precedes a word, "w+slash" are used: w/ribs (p. 5), w/sweet (p. 8), w/out (p.11), w/flesh (p. 11) all in efforts to demonstrate "how words determine our representations of self and other" (Chamberlain 1996, p. 33).

Brathwaite questions the fact that the authority of the written word is readily acknowledged and disseminated. As soon as the word is written, it is received as "holy writ and late holly". Mackey (1996) says, the word's "monumental premises" are established. Thus, the main function of this linguistic subversion at the explicit level is to show "the divisibility and the alterability of words, their permeability to alternate arrangement, variability, change" (p. 139). This clearly confirms Brathwaite's perception of the word which he expresses in 'Veve':

For on this ground trampled with the bull's swathe of whips where
the slave at the crossroads was a red anthill eaten by moonbeams,
by the holy ghosts of his wounds the Word becomes again a god and
walks among us; look, here are his rags, here is his crutch and his
satchel of dreams; here is his hoe and his rude implements on this
ground on this broken ground
(*The Arrivants*, p. 263)

Thus, the word is not strange to Brathwaite. He therefore, possesses the license to twist it to suit his social and cultural demands and Brathwaite has accomplished this to a greater degree. Brathwaite's verbal dexterity helps him in his bid to capture several unrelated themes and motifs from colonial history to personal tragedy and to the modern Caribbean history in *Born to Slow Horses*.

Brathwaite effectively uses pun to invent and discover other meanings of words and thus emphasises the impression of the authority upon words. This style often throws readers into a state of imbalance slowing down the reading and at the same time forcing readers to process the words to get likely meanings expressed. In 'The Masters of Mary Jones' tale' and 'tail' are combined to re-inscribe the Caribbean history where image of the sea is prominent. Tail refers to past of a being and tale refers to story:

It have come to his *tail* from the web tides Out of the wood and the
wave leave watch of his lonely fisherman's sea and that night it is
scale with the Milky Way green star flame and blue fish foam and
its *tale* it make of the night watch bumps of smaller travelling fish
harbouring under the boat and its sailing eyes is the night wich
moon and the water star strike bright (*BTSH*, p. 4).

In ‘Kumina’, ‘socks, and ‘shocks’; ‘sun’ and ‘sun’; ‘death’ and ‘debt’ are played upon suggesting though different but related meanings on close assessment.

demtief-off evva thing they fine pun Mark So when he went down to the policestation morgue that night My son mange up widdoutim shoes &shocks on the fourteenth day after my sun gone, on the first day after him entomb i feel my womb (BTSH, p. 78)

“Socks” are worn on the feet with shoes while ‘shocks’ suggests the cease of his movement as a dead person cannot move; ‘death’ is seen as a ‘debt’ that Mark in this poem has paid; ‘son’ refers to Mark the son of the persona while ‘sun’ suggests that the deceased is the persona’s source of joy and light; ‘tired’ is used to coin ‘tireen(th)’ by removing sound /t/ for sound effect; fubjeting replaces forgetting or fidgeting while. In ‘Hawk’ “murdered” is used to depict the world as a place of disasters and at the same time ‘a mother’ of all beings. Thus, Brathwaite revised words and concepts that come to the poet through the imposed language. With this experiment, he crosses the cultural borders in new and experimental ways by “arrest[ing] the linguistic sign in its symbolic function” (Bhabha 2005, p. 69). These linguistic deviations can be described as violent linguistic revolution that is in agreement with Fanon’s preaching of physical violence against the colonial subjugation. The new forms is an informed steps towards gaining freedom for the natives.

Conclusion

This paper has not only established Fanon’s writings as the foundation of the postcolonial aesthetics, but it has also detailed how his politics of race and colonialism informed the concept of aesthetics in a postcolonial context. His works on native writers’ development, synthesis of cultural ethics and language in a multicultural society like Caribbean have encouraged writers of postcolonial contexts found means to rebel against the colonisers’ cultures and languages. Though Fanon has been accused of overgeneralization in his works, it is pertinent to state the fact that every writer in postcolonial contexts must have gone through some of, if not all, the stages Fanon mentioned in his books. Edward Kamau Brathwaite, whose primary texts were adopted for this study, demonstrates most of the qualities though not exactly as Fanon organized them in the three stages. It is observed that Brathwaite cultivated his Caribbean vision of Africa early in his writing. He did not stay for long in Fanon’s first stage, if he stayed at all. He realised the duty literary writers owe the Caribbean multicultural society early and take up the task as a defender of the African culture and its mouthpiece. All his works resonate the vision from his first major collection, *The Arrivants* (1967), to one of his last works, *Born to Slow Horses* (2005).

Postcolonial literature is a field that calls for more researches, especially in exploring its aesthetics. Its engagement with politics does not negate the aspect of its aesthetics in any way. There is need to concentrate on what constitute its aesthetics in other genres and cultures.

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